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Political and psychological factors that influence intention to recycle

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Highlights

- Trust in governments influences the acceptance of public policies as it reduces uncertainty.
- Habits play a moderating role between reliability and acceptance of policies.
- People who accept a public recycling policy express their intentions to recycle.
- Individuals concerned about an environmental policy accept public policies that promote recycling.
- Social pressure positively influences the intention to recycle while time risks do so negatively.

Political and psychological factors that influence intention to recycle

Abstract

This research proposes a causal model that studies the influence of both political (trust in government and concern about the policy designed) and psychological factors (social influence and perceived risks) on the intention to recycle. It also addresses the moderating role of habits in the processes of acceptance of public recycling policies. To evaluate a new public policy for urban waste management in Córdoba city (Argentina) a structural equation model with 350 individuals was developed. Thus, it is confirmed that trust reduces uncertainty and favours the acceptance of a public policy, especially to those individuals who do not recycle and do not understand the benefits of new regulations. Besides, individuals concerned with the design of a public policy tend to accept them, denoting the relevance of environmental awareness in the implementation of recycling actions. Finally, political factors, social pressure and perceived risks are relevant psychological antecedents that explain the intention to recycle.

Keywords: policy, trust, acceptance, intention, recycling, habits.

1. Introduction

Governments must design public policies to mitigate environmental damage and make transformative and systematic changes (United Nations, 2021). Thus, they develop regulations that restrict individual behaviour and that require the involvement of citizens for their compliance (Kim et al., 2013). Therefore, it is relevant to understand the variables that influence citizens' acceptance of policies since the expected results depend on their active participation (Kyselá et al., 2019; De Groot and Schuitema, 2012). In this framework, there is no consensus on what the acceptance of a policy implies and on what the indicators for its measurement are (Kim and Shim, 2020).

In particular, public policies for the management of urban solid waste (USW) aim to preserve natural resources through three activities: reduction, reuse and recycling of waste. USW is based on the active participation of citizens in household waste separation at the expense of their time and education. In this context, the recycling regulations proposed by governments frequently call for voluntary contributions without monetary compensation, so they require communications to demonstrate the social benefit derived from individual behaviours. Accordingly, previous studies have suggested that political aspects such as trust in the government and the quality of the proposed regulations influence citizens' acceptance of policies (Siegrist et al., 2002). Hence, it is necessary to understand the scope of political factors depending on the environmental behaviour of citizens since there is evidence that individuals' habits moderate the impact of trust in governments on the acceptance of a policy (Chiu et al. al., 2012).

Wan et al. (2018) consider the influence of political variables as well as the psychological (or intrinsic) factors that predispose individuals to adopt government regulations. In the recycling context, the theory of planned behaviour assumes that if a person gets a benefit from recycling, he/she will have greater intentions to carry out such behaviour despite the cost that it will incur to separate waste at home (Onel and Mukherjee, 2017). Recycling also promotes a set of values that facilitate individual behaviour but only if they are shared by a social group. Thus, social influence is a precedent that must be considered in recycling studies.

The objective of this study is to confirm the causal chain of political and psychological factors on citizens' intentions to recycle; therefore, we propose a model of structural equations to study how recycling intentions develop, considering individual costs, social pressures and the acceptance of a recycling policy determined by trust in governments and their regulations. To this end, citizens' opinion on a recycling policy launched in 2018 in Córdoba city (Argentina) was evaluated, which

involved an intensive communication program (Municipality of Córdoba, 2021). For the first time, the city designed a policy that integrated education campaigns on how to separate waste and where to dispose of it and the government purchased collection vehicles and established routes for the removal of recycled waste.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents the theoretical framework and the justification for the conceptual development of this study. Section 3 describes the research methodology. Descriptive findings are reported in section 4, and section 5, includes conclusions and implications on how to promote recycling intentions and the design of public policies.

2. Theoretical framework

2.1.1 Trust and acceptance of public policies

Citizen's trust in a government is the belief that it will be able to achieve its objectives because it is perceived as competent and with values and intentions aligned with those of its citizens (Greenberg, 2014). High levels of trust in the government allow citizens to reduce the complexity and uncertainty in making their individual decisions, which facilitates the implementation and legitimation of public policies (Zannakis et al., 2015).

Hence, trust is an underlying attitude of citizens towards public policy, which can be expressed in open (e.g., respecting a legal norm or defending an environmental cause) or hidden (e.g., expressing an opinion) behaviours. However, the acceptance of a public policy implies that citizens are willing to commit to regulations and to modify their behaviours based on what governments establish (Stern, 2000). This acceptance implies a benefit that citizens deduce after analysing the costs and risks of the new behaviour (Degroot et al., 2013).

In the field of USW policies, trust in the authorities increases domestic recycling actions (Nguyen et al., 2015), promotes support (Mukai et al., 2020) and influences perceptions of governments' management capacity (Loan et al., 2017). In addition, there is evidence on the direct and causal relationship between trust and the acceptance of public policies (Kollemann and Reichl, 2015), so it is possible to hypothesize that:

H₁: Political trust directly and positively influences the acceptance of public USW policies.

2.1.2 Recycling habits and acceptance of public policies

The management of USW policies represents a challenge to governments as it requires a change in their citizens' habits. Habits are memory-based tendencies to automatically respond to specific signals that are acquired through the repetition of behaviours in stable contexts (Verplanken and Whitmarsh, 2021). Thus, when a person has acquired a habit, his/her behaviour becomes routine, lacking in planning and with limited conscious effort (Lavelle et al., 2015). Previous studies have examined the moderating role of habits since they affect behavioural intentions when there is certain level of automation (Jorgensen et al., 2013). Indeed, Chiu et al. (2012) observed that when a new behaviour becomes a habit, that is, automatic and familiar, it is because there is no longer any uncertainty regarding the decision whether to recycle or not and, therefore, the effect of whether to trust or not on the acceptance of policies diminishes. In this context, people who have recycling habits will sustain their behaviour over time (Knussen et al., 2004). It is expected that they support initiatives that are familiar to them, having less impact on the trust placed in the government as a predictor variable of policy acceptance. Consequently, it is proposed that:

H_{1b}: Recycling habits negatively moderate the impact of trust in the acceptance of USW public policies.

2.2. Concern about the reliability of the waste separation policy and its impact on acceptance

In developing countries, citizens do not collaborate with the recycling process when they perceive that their classified waste at home is then mixed during transport or in subsequent treatment (Loan et al., 2017). When citizens perceive that their effort does not generate benefits, the effectiveness of the USW policy is undermined since its success is based on the sum of individual behaviours (Harring et al., 2019). Besides, there is resistance in the implementation of a public policy when there is uncertainty about the operation of the actions prescribed by the government (Steg and Vleck, 2009). However, when the competent authority provides the necessary infrastructure, it facilitates cooperation (Mansbridge, 2014) as citizens perceive that public policy is correctly designed, is efficient and brings benefits (Loan et al., 2017). When the recycling system is reliable, a collective moral norm is formed that forces individual behaviour (Miliute-Plepiene et al., 2016).

In this context, insofar as citizens are involved in understanding the benefits and operation of a USW policy, they express a degree of concern about policies that seek environmental care and that leads them to make sacrifices within the established regulations (Hedlund, 2011), affecting their intentions (Sarabia-Sánchez et al., 2021). When citizens worry about the reliability of a recycling system, they show their environmental awareness and are predisposed to accept USW policies (Lee and Paik, 2011). Therefore, it is feasible to hypothesize that:

H₂: Concern about the reliability of a USW policy directly and positively influences acceptance of public policy.

2.3. Acceptance of public policies and their impact on the intention to recycle

Acceptance implies that citizens have positive attitudes towards new procedures, laws or taxes, all of which make the policy and the effectiveness of its implementation viable (Wan et al., 2015). Indeed, the acceptance of a public policy implies that the citizen is willing to participate (Stern, 2000), positively evaluating the changes in the public context (Rodríguez-Sánchez et al., 2018). In this sense, it is relevant to distinguish public policy acceptance, defined as an attitude, from public support. Public support represents the intention to take actions related to such policies (Jansson and Rezvani, 2019). Thus, acceptance of a public policy can be conceptualized as an antecedent of public support and the intention to recycle. Accordingly, in a study on the promotion of solar thermal tanks and alternative fuel vehicles, Chen et al. (2016) found evidence that attitude positively affects the intention to incorporate sustainable behaviours. Therefore, it is possible to hypothesize that:

H₃: Acceptance of the USW public policy directly and positively influences intention to recycle.

2.4. Social influence and its impact on the intention to recycle

Social influence is defined as a change in an individual's thoughts, feelings, attitudes, or behaviours that results from interaction with another individual or a group. Social influence is a construct with a strong impact on the processes of adoption of habits and consumption (Rashotte 2007). Also, Korir and Kipkemboi (2014) define social influence as the pressure exerted by a group to encourage a person to change his/her attitudes to conform to the group's norms. Thus, social influence implies persuading or urging others to do something or to keep from doing something else and it involves changing one's behaviour to meet social approval (Farrow et al., 2017). In this research, it suggests that individuals are permeable to family, neighbours and friends' advice about waste recycling (Labib et al., 2021), which predisposes them to act in a prosocial way (Xu et al., 2018).

The individual experiences a psychological pressure that arises from comparing his/her behaviour with that of others, which generates feelings of guilt, and prompts them to change their attitude and behaviour (Daido, 2004); hence, social influence promotes intrinsic motivations (Ling et al.,

2021). Similarly, previous studies have indicated that social influences positively affect the purchase intention of green products (Chen et al., 2018), as well as the intention to recycle (Labib et al., 2021) and the frequency of recycling (Blöse et al., 2020). Therefore, it is hypothesized that:

H₄: Social influence directly and positively influences intention to recycle.

2.5. Individual time risks as antecedents of intention

Risk perception is defined as the process of interpreting signals and forming a subjective judgment about the probable damage that uncertain events could cause (Bradley et al., 2020). Perceived risks are unique to each person based on their values, education, experiences, and interests (Robinson et al., 2012). Perceived risk is a construct with multiple dimensions (social, financial, psychological, performance, physical and temporal) that vary in preponderance according to the phenomenon under study (Rodríguez-Sánchez and Sarabia-Sánchez, 2016). These dimensions, or components of risk, negatively influence intention, so it is expected that people with low aversion to risk have a greater behavioural intention (Martins et al., 2014). Time risk is one of the dimensions of risk perception and it implies an analysis of the potential loss of time caused by a new behaviour as a result of a new learning process (Chang and Tseng, 2013). Time risks affects household waste separation because it requires that citizens carry out a set of frequent practices (Chai et al., 2015). Furthermore, if the recycling activity is a voluntary behaviour without economic incentives, it can be perceived as an action that takes up free time and has an opportunity cost (Halvorsen, 2008). This perception could explain the gap between the intention to care for the environment and actual behaviour because if environmental behaviour (e.g., recycling) requires a lot of time and effort, it probably will not be adopted. Thus, lack of free time inhibits people's desire to behave in accordance with their underlying environmental concerns (Chai et al. 2015), and, therefore, a negative relationship between perceived time risks and behavioural intention is assumed (Hubert et al., 2019). Then, it is proposed that:

H₅: Perceived time risks directly and negatively influence intention to recycle.

3. Methodology

3.1. Procedure and participants

A questionnaire with the research interest scales was designed for the first phase of the work. The information collection system used was through a PAPI (paper and pencil interview) as some questions required the interviewer's intervention. An effective sample of 350 individuals was obtained, for which interviewers were assigned to eight government offices of Córdoba city which bring together neighbourhoods with different socioeconomic status. Therefore, socioeconomic status quotas were imposed (ABC1 = 6%, C2 = 18%, C3 = 31% and D1D2 = 46%) according to a report of the Argentine Society of Marketing and Opinion Researchers (SAIMO, 2012): age (with year intervals of 18-35, 36-45, 46-55, 56-65 and over 65) and sex (men and women), respecting the proportions of the last population census (INDEC, 2010).

3.2. Measurements

The scales used (see Appendix), which had been validated in previous studies, were adapted to the Spanish language of Argentina. 7-point Likert-type scales were used, in which 1 = "totally disagree", 7 = "totally agree", and 4 = "neither disagree nor agree".

Intention to recycle. The scale used by Ramayah et al. (2012) in their study on urban recycling was chosen.

Acceptance of public policies. The scale used by Rodríguez-Sánchez et al. (2018) was adopted. Yet, the items were adapted to analyse the evaluation of urban recycling policies.

Trust in government. The Poortinga and Pidgeon's (2006) scale was used to measure people's willingness to trust those responsible for designing recycling policies.

Concern about the reliability of the recycling policy. The three-item scale from Loan et al. (2017) was adapted to measure concern about USW policy, guiding the writing to evaluate citizen's level of interest in its operation, benefits and reliability.

Social Influence. It was taken from the work of Sinnappan and Rahman (2011) to measure an individual's peer influence on decision making regarding recycling.

Perceived time risk. The Featherman and Pavlou (2003) scale was adapted to evaluate the opinion about the time it takes an individual to learn and carry out home recycling tasks.

Recycling Habits. To carry out a moderation analysis, the individuals were classified into two groups according to their answer to the question: "Do you separate waste (paper-plastic-glass-organic) at home?" This question had a frequency score of 1 to 5, in which 1 was "I never recycle" and 5 was "I always recycle." Consequently, a group with higher recycling habits (individuals with scores of 4 and 5), and another without recycling habits (subjects with scores 1, 2 and 3) were formed. Through Student's t tests, it was shown that the conformed groups have a significant mean difference.

4. Results

The analyses were carried out using the two-step method proposed by Anderson and Gerbing (1988), which first involves a confirmatory factor analysis to validate the measurement model (reliability and validity) and later an analysis of structural equations to verify the raised hypotheses. Reliability problems were not detected since all Cronbach's alphas and composite reliability indices of the factors are higher than the recommended value of 0.7. Besides, all the extracted variances are greater than 0.50 (Fornell and Larcker, 1981). Then, to guarantee convergent validity, we eliminated the items with factor loadings lower than 0.70 (Bagozzi and Yi, 1988), being these: CG4, CG5, PA2, PA3, SI3 and RT4. This strategy does not produce significant decreases in content validity due to the elimination of the low percentages of indicators (Bell and Lumsden, 1980) (see Table 1).

Here Table 1

Discriminant validity problems were not identified since (see Table 2): a) the heterotrait-monotrait ratio is less than 0.9 for each pair of factors (Henseler et al., 2016) and b) the average variance extracted for each factor is always higher than the square of the correlation between each pair of factors (Fornell and Larcker, 1981).

Here Table 2

The estimation method used has been the robust maximum likelihood (RML), which is adequate to overcome the problems of non-normality of the data as the calculated Mardia coefficient is 64.34. RML uses Satorra-Bentler scaled χ^2 statistic (S-B χ^2) to improve the reliability of the standard errors and of the statistic in the absence of normality (Aldás and Uriel, 2017). However, it is a statistic that is sensitive to sample size and deviations from multivariate normality, so it tends to be significant (Bentler and Bonnett, 1980). Thus, we justify the good fit of the model by calculating the quotient between the S-B χ^2 and its degrees of freedom, which assumes a value

lower than 5 (Wheaton et al., 1977). Besides, considering that such quotient has the same limitations of χ^2 , we completed the evaluation of the fit with indicators of goodness of fit (Hair et al., 2005). Therefore, the fit of the measurement model is good (see Table 2). Finally, we tested the hypotheses using a covariance structure model whose resulting fit is good (see Table 3). For the contrasts of invariance form, load factor and factor variance (for the proposed moderation hypothesis) we used the multigroup analysis technique following the methodological guidelines of Aldás (2013).

Here Table 3

4.2 Hypothesis testing

Analyses confirm that both trust in the government ($\beta_1 = 0.169$; $p > 0.05$; Cohen's $d = 0.093$; acceptance of H_1) and concern about the reliability of public policy ($\beta_2 = 0.214$; $p > 0.01$; Cohen's $d = 0.118$; acceptance of H_2) influence the acceptance of public policies. Besides, both the acceptance of public policies ($\beta_3 = 0.299$; $p < 0.01$; Cohen's $d = 0.263$; acceptance of H_3) and social influence ($\beta_4 = 0.220$; $p < 0.01$; Cohen's $d = 0.253$; acceptance of H_4) positively influence citizens' intention to recycle. Furthermore, time risk negatively influences recycling intentions ($\beta_5 = -0.320$; $p < 0.01$; Cohen's $d = -0.324$; acceptance of H_5).

Table 4 shows the results of the multi-group analysis that includes the estimation of the structural relationships for each group and their corresponding goodness-of-fit measures exceeding the critical acceptance values, and thus presenting a good fit. According to the analysis of the Lagrange test on the significance of the S-B χ^2 difference, recycling habits are significantly different between groups. When considering H_{1b} , recycling habits modify the strength of the structural relationship between trust in the government and acceptance of public policies, constituting a moderating variable.

Trust in the government does not significantly influence the acceptance of public policies ($\beta_{1b1} = -0.0051$; $t = 0.588$, Cohen's $d = 0.04$) when a person has recycling habits. On the contrary, in those people who do not have recycling habits, trust in the government is an antecedent that significantly influences acceptance ($\beta_{1b2} = 0.265$; $t = 2.622$; Cohen's $d = 0.19$).

Here Table 4

A summary of the results of the present work is shown in Figure 1.

Here Figure 1

5. Conclusions

The results confirm that trust in the government positively influences the acceptance of public recycling policies (H_1). This finding is consistent with the literature regarding environmental policies in general as well as recycling policies in particular (Wan, 2017), observing its role as a facilitator of citizen cooperation (Loan et al., 2017). People accept voluntary efforts to recycle their waste if they perceive the government as an entity capable of managing USW policies. On the other hand, many citizens have limited knowledge about recycling so they doubt the efficiency of their decisions. Hence, trust reduces the uncertainty about the environmental problem that this public policy seeks to mitigate (Wan, 2018; Zannakis et al., 2015).

However, results show that the impact of trust in the acceptance of public policies is direct and positive in citizens who do not have built-in recycling habits and habits negatively moderate the impact of trust on the acceptance of public policies (acceptance of H_{1b}). Indeed, people who

already have recycling habits do not need to trust the government to accept a new policy, since they have enough experience and information to commit themselves to the standard. This is confirmed when analysing the effect size of trust in the acceptance of public policies: trust explains acceptance only when individuals have not incorporated recycling habits ($d = 0.19$ for the group without habits versus $d = 0.04$ for the group with habits). Thus, this research highlights the importance of examining the moderating effect of the factors that influence acceptance of public policies (Wan, 2018).

With regard to the positive relationship between concern about reliability of public policy and its influence on acceptance by individuals (acceptance of H_2), we understand that the result is logical. Individuals' concern about correct policy operation influences their conscious intentions (Sarabia-Sánchez et al., 2021). People are involved in understanding the design, operation and impacts of the recycling system, everything which reduces uncertainty and facilitates adoption. Such concern is necessarily a consequence of high levels of citizens' environmental awareness to understand the advantages of a USW policy (Loan et al., 2017). Therefore, all recycling communications from governments should include both aspects related to the effectiveness of the program's operation and information that promotes environmental awareness.

Furthermore, individuals' concern about the design of public policies should not be conceived as a restriction on their implementation, but rather as a possibility of gaining support (Lee and Paik, 2011). Indeed, concern will promote citizen involvement by reducing individual resistance to the extent that the policy is properly designed. In addition, it will allow governments to design valued public policies, facilitating their continuity over time. Although the size of the effect of citizens' concern about the operation of a policy is low ($d = 0.118$), its contribution is significant and explains the importance of political factors in citizens' adoption of sustainable practices. (Wan et al., 2018).

In line with Chen et al. (2016), we have also verified the direct and positive relationship between public policy acceptance and intention to recycle (H_3). Citizens' positive attitude towards new regulations encourages them to carry out sustainable behaviours promoted by USW policy. In turn, the direct and positive role of social influence in the intention to recycle is confirmed (Labib et al., 2021), denoting the central role of primary groups that share values, beliefs and thoughts (acceptance of H_4). Moreover, social influence encourages or presses individuals, promoting both an intrinsic motivation (Ling et al., 2021) and a way of acting in a prosocial way (Xu et al., 2018).

Regarding the negative relationship between time risk and recycling intentions (H_5), the result is logical because if a person perceives that separating waste will lead to a significant loss of his/her discretionary time, his /her intention to recycle will decrease. We observed that the risk effect size on intentions is low ($d = -0.324$), however, it is the model variable with the greatest explanatory power. Therefore, people take into account the opportunity cost of the recycling effort, since the behaviour requested is voluntary and altruistic. Thus, government communications should clearly inform about the benefits of recycling and report on the efficiency of the USW policy to overcome the costs associated with recycling (Halvorsen, 2008).

On the other hand, this research has some limitations. First, it was carried out only in Córdoba city; therefore, the results cannot be generalized to another population as they may be influenced by cultural factors. Second, the trust-in-government construct was studied at the aggregate level without differentiating other political factors such as individual's confidence in political personalities, political parties or political instruments (Wan et al., 2017). Last, a novel USW policy was evaluated so that individuals were in the process of learning about its operation.

Future studies on the current topic are therefore recommended. Firstly, it is relevant to replicate the model in different socioeconomic and cultural contexts. Secondly, these causal relationships should be studied in other public policies that promote pro-environmental behaviours such as saving water or adopting sustainable energy. Finally, it would be useful to consider trust as a

multidimensional construct to study in detail its dimensions and the acceptance of environmental public policies.

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APPENDIX - Scales used

Constructo	Ítem	Indicador	Fuente
Intention to recycle	IR1	I intend to participate in the recycling behaviour in the coming months.	Ramayah et al. (2012)
	IR2	I will try to participate in the recycling behaviour in the coming months.	
	IR3	I am looking forward to participating in the recycling Beauvoir in the coming months.	
Policy acceptance	PA1	I agree that the Municipality implements policies aimed at home separation.	Rodríguez Sánchez et al. (2018)
	PA2	What is your position when discussing about the household waste separation policy with your family and friends?	
	PA3	When did you start separating waste at home?	
	PA4	I accept the municipal policy for the separation of household waste.	
	PA5	I agree with the home waste separation policy.	
Trust in government	TG1	The Municipality is doing a good job in urban recycling.	Poortinga and Pidgeon (2006)
	TG2	The Municipality acts in the interest of the public good.	
	TG3	The Municipality is competent enough.	
	TG4	The Municipality listens to what ordinary people think.	
	TG5	In general, I trust the government of Córdoba city.	
Concern about the reliability of the policy	CON1	I am concerned whether the waste separation policy will work as well as it is supposed to.	Loan et al. (2017)
	CON2	I am concerned that the waste separation policy will not provide the benefits I expect	
	CON3	I am concerned about the reliability of the waste separation policy.	
Social influence	SI1	I learn a lot about recycling and waste separation from my friends.	Sinnappan and Rahman (2011)
	SI2	I learn a lot about environmental issues from my friends.	
	SI3	With my friends, we often buy recyclable products.	
	SI4	I share information on ecological issues with my friends.	
Risk of time	RT1	I think I will waste more time separating the waste.	Featherman and Pavlou (2003)
	RT2	As I change how I manage trash, separating waste at home will take more time.	
	RT3	It would be tough to spend time separating waste.	
	RT4	The possible loss of time due to having to separate waste would be high.	

TABLE 1
Psychometric properties of the measurement model: reliability and convergent validity

Factor	Item	λ (t-value)	Reliability		
			α	CR	AVE
Trust in government	CG1	0.791 (17.026)**	0.826	0.828	0.618
	CG2	0.837 (18.977)**			
	CG3	0.723 (14.317)**			
Concern about the reliability of the Policy	CON1	0.898 (20.156)**	0.904	0.904	0.759
	CON2	0.852 (17.475)**			
	CON3	0.863 (18.976)**			
Policy acceptance	PA1	0.688 (7.549)**	0.850	0.855	0.665
	PA4	0.821 (9.147)**			
	PA5	0.944 (9.712)**			
Social influence	SI1	0.925 (28.189)**	0.874	0.883	0.719
	SI2	0.905 (25.578)**			
	SI4	0.693 (15.255)**			
Risk of time	RT1	0.867 (18.774)**	0.890	0.892	0.736
	RT2	0.879 (24.197)**			
	RT3	0.822 (16.182)**			
Intention to recycle	IR1	0.838 (13.569)**	0.860	0.860	0.673
	IR2	0.744 (12.089)**			
	IR3	0.889 (13.548)**			
Robust Adjustment Goodness Measures					
S-B χ^2 (120df) =169.51 (p=0.002)		SRMR	TLI	CFI	RMSEA (90% CI)
		0.05	0.975	0.981	0.041 (0.025 0.054)

Notes: λ = Standardized factor loading, α = Cronbach's α , CR = Composite Reliability, AVE = Average variance extracted, S-B χ^2 = χ^2 Satorra-Bentler, df = degrees of freedom, SRMR= Standardized Root Mean Residual TLI = Tucker-Lewis Index, CFI = Comparative Fit Index, RMSEA = Root Mean-Square Error of Approximation, CI = Confidence Interval, **=<0.05.

TABLE 2
Psychometric properties of the measurement model: discriminant validity

Factor	Risk of time	Concern	Social influence	Trust in government	Policy acceptance	Intention to recycle
Risk of time	0.736	0.003	0.052	0.012	0.107	0.201
Concern about the reliability of the Policy	0.065	0.759	0.000	0.003	0.039	0.071
Social influence	0.286	0.055	0.719	0.041	0.040	0.116
Trust in government	0.114	0.070	0.208	0.618	0.021	0.036
Policy acceptance	0.369	0.226	0.231	0.157	0.665	0.174
Intention to recycle	0.450	0.264	0.391	0.193	0.422	0.673

Notes. Values of the Average Variance Index (AVE) in main diagonal. Lower triangular matrix: Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio of Correlations. Upper triangular matrix: correlations between the factors.

TABLE 3
Structural equation model results

Hypothesis	Structural relationship	Std. coefficient	t-Value	Contrast	
H ₁	Trust in government → Policy acceptance	0.169	2.248**	<i>Accepted</i>	
H ₂	Concern about the reliability of the Policy → Policy acceptance	0.214	2.766***	<i>Accepted</i>	
H ₃	Policy acceptance → Intention to recycle	0.299	4.163***	<i>Accepted</i>	
H ₄	Social influence → Intention to recycle	0.220	3.957***	<i>Accepted</i>	
H ₅	Risk of time → Intention to recycle	-0.320	-5.072***	<i>Accepted</i>	
Robust Adjustment Goodness Measures					
S-B χ^2 (124df) = 205.45 (p = 0.000)		SRMR	TLI	CFI	RMSEA (90% CI)
		0.088	0.961	0.968	0.043 (0.039 0.063)

Notes. * = p<0.1; **p = <0.05; ***= p<0.01, S-B χ^2 = χ^2 Satorra-Bentler, df = degrees of freedom, SRMR= Standardized Root Mean Residual, TLI = Tucker-Lewis Index, CFI = Comparative Fit Index, RMSEA = Root Mean-Square Error of Approximation, CI = Confidence Interval.

TABLE 4
Moderating effect of Recycling Habits

Hypothesis	Structural Relationship	Multigroup Model*						Lagrange's Test			Contrast
		General Model†		With recycling habit		Without recycling habit		Diff. χ^2 (accumulated)	df	P-Value	
		β	t-value	β	t-value	β	t-value				
H1 _B	<i>Recycling habits negatively moderate the impact of trust in the acceptance of USW public policies</i>	0.169	2.248	0.051	0.588 ^{NS}	0,265	2.622***	6.060	1	0.014	<i>Accepted</i>

† General Model Settings:

S-B χ^2 (124df) = 205.45 (p<0.01); SRMR=0,088 TLI = 0.961; CFI = 0.968; RMSEA = 0.043 (0.039–0.063).

* Multigroup model settings

S-B χ^2 (255df) = 435.69 (p<0.01); TLI = 0.975; CFI = 0.983; RMSEA = 0.034 (0.020–0.057).

Notes. * = p<0.1; **p <0.05; *** = p<0.01, NS = Not Significant, β = Standard Coefficient, S-B χ^2 = χ^2 Satorra-Bentler, df = degrees of freedom, TLI = Tucker-Lewis Index, CFI = Comparative Fit Index, RMSEA = Root Mean-Square Error of Approximation.

FIGURE 1
Structural Relations Model

Notes. * = $p < 0.1$; ** = $p < 0.05$; *** = $p < 0.01$, NS = Not Significant, β = Standard Coefficient, t = t-value.